

ACCEPTABILITY OF VEGETARIAN WORK PACKETS IN AN ONLINE DISTANCE LEARNING CLASSROOM FOR BREAD AND PASTRY PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT

Acceptability of online distance learning on vegetarian work packets and the skills performance of grade 10 students in bread and pastry production was examined. The descriptive correlational research design was utilized to 55 respondents who were Grade 10 students enrolled in an online distance learning modality at Lipa Adventist Academy, Bugtong, Lipa City, Batangas during the onset of the Covid 19 pandemic. The gathering of data used a survey questionnaire rendered thru Google form. Statistical treatments used were mean, frequency count and percentage, mean and standard deviation, and Pearson's Correlation Coefficient. Data results revealed the acceptability of online distance learning on vegetarian work packets aspects as to its content, usability user-friendliness, relevance, economy, efficiency, and availability is significantly related to students' performance in thinking skills in terms of conceptualization and analysis and their technical skills in terms of engagement, exploration, explanation, elaboration, and evaluation is significant. Thus, the hypothesis, there is no significant relationship between the acceptability of the respondents on the aspects of the online distance learning on vegetarian work packets and students' skills performance in bread and pastry production was not sustained. Gathered data and analysis were generally acceptable but can still be improved at a higher acceptability range. In this regard, teachers may employ additional teaching-learning strategies to enhance online teaching implementation. Students can be directed to help improve thinking and technical skills. Further study may use this study to serve as baseline data on recent trends in education. Administrators might support teachers with opportunities to engage in professional learning experiences and work collaboratively to design learning schemes.

Keywords: Acceptability, Bread and Pastry Production, Classroom Skills Performance, Online Distance Learning, Vegetarian Work Packets